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USE OF NEW TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC

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The Republic of Uzbekistan is committed to creating conditions for the development of all types of creativity in the path of its spiritual renewal, to the development of the young generation in all aspects, and to the work of developing the creativity and abilities of young people regardless of their nationality and race. paying attention is one of the urgent problems of today. This requires further improvement of educational and educational work in general education schools, achieving the commonality of education and training. The goal of music education is to raise the young generation to the level of a cultured person who can inherit our national musical heritage and perceive universal musical values.

Music teaching methodology and pedagogy is an important factor in determining the content and quality of education, using the most advanced, effective, practically tested and effective methods and tools used in the process of education and training. The introduction of new pedagogic, innovative teaching technologies into the educational system, rapid changes in the field of science and technology require specific updates in the field of education as well.

Story telling method

This method is a description of the music teacher's musical work based on vivid, emotional, bright life events and concrete historical evidence, literary and artistic

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scenes, and the purpose of its application is to familiarize students with the musical work, its genre, and its performance style. It aims to get acquainted with the aspects of traditionality, artistic and ideological content, in what situation, by whom and in what order, as well as in-depth and complete information about skilled performers and authors. Students should know about our great ancestors and scientists who grew up on the soil of Central Asia and made a great contribution to the development of world science and culture, including the art of music, and whose services are recognized all over the world.

Therefore, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abdul Qadir Maroghi, Az-Zamakhshari, Darvish Ali Changi, Abdurrahman Jami, who were great philosophers, encyclopedists, and in turn made a great contribution to the development of the science of music. , along with the great services of thinkers like Kavkabi in the field of science, to explain the information about their works on the theory of music, musical notes, and the characteristics of the structure of musical sounds in connection with their discoveries in the fields of medicine, mathematics, geography, literature and other sciences. or it can be told based on available additional materials and information on these subjects. The stories can be about the life and work of some artists, works that have a special place in the Uzbek national music culture (they can also be about modern works or the work of composers), epics, status art, folk art.

Visual teaching method

It is known that music consists of a moving melody and a system of harmonized sounds. It can be perceived only by listening through the organs of hearing. It is very important to use the visual method to write musical notes beautifully

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(according to the rules of good writing, etiquette) based on the knowledge of painting and drawing.

The students' knowledge and skills in painting and drawing will come in handy in such activities as conducting schemes, showing the drawing images of dance movements on a blackboard, poster, writing them in their notebooks, and drawing their pictures based on the images of the work. In this place, the teacher's pedagogic skills, eloquence, directing skills play an important role.

In general, each subject is to some extent connected with other subjects in a unique way and in a way that this connection is more and more vivid in the teaching process related to the theoretical and practical performance of music. appears. Therefore, a reasonable and appropriate use of the connection and connection of disciplines requires a music teacher to have broad knowledge in all disciplines and sufficient knowledge, theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities of several areas of musical art. requires having. Organization of music lessons in interdisciplinary connection, use of advanced innovative technologies, advanced work experiences, creation and application of new and effective work methods and forms is the demand of the times.

References

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